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Editorial on Issues of Neo-Lithics’ Self-Perception, and on Periodisation, Epochal Narratives, and Hope

This editorial¹ is bipartite. It addresses, first, a matter of *Neo-Lithics* self-perception, and secondly, it turns to the question of periodisation, epochal narratives, and the moral responsibilities of archaeological scholarship in times of war, polarisation, and historical anxiety.

Since its foundation in 1994, *Neo-Lithics* has operated as an independent forum within Neolithic research. It has also offered space for innovative, non-aligned, and at times deliberately debatable contributions, provided that they met academic standards and possessed the potential to initiate, redirect, question, or scrutinise current research trends. The newsletter has never understood academic quality as identical with conformity. Rather, it has sought to maintain a productive tension between scholarly rigour and intellectual openness.² This tension is not always comfortable; yet it is precisely where a living discipline proves its resilience.

In this respect, the axiom-driven contribution by C. Bodet in the present issue, proposing an “exogamic key” to the symbolic language of the Göbekli Cultures, represents an extreme case. Its argument commits itself with unusual determination to a single explanatory model, prioritising selected

evidence in support of a strongly focused interpretation, and in some respects returning to older conceptual frameworks. The strictness, epistemological narrowness, and heuristic one-sidedness of the paper triggered an intense internal debate, both academic and editorial. Regrettably, this debate contributed to Marion Benz’s decision to leave the editorial board, after many years of substantial and devoted service to *Neo-Lithics*.

We therefore wish to state, with sincere gratitude, how much *Neo-Lithics* owes to Marion Benz’s long-standing commitment, intellectual engagement, and editorial labour. Her contribution to the journal has been significant, and it remains part of its history.

The decision by Anna Belfer-Cohen and Hans Georg K. Gebel to uphold publication of Bodet’s article was not an endorsement of its argument in any programmatic sense. It was, rather, a decision in favour of academic freedom and critical debate. The hope is that a provocative and contestable contribution might stimulate other research into the iconographic codes of Southeast Anatolia’s and the North Levantine PPNA symbolic sphere, precisely by inviting contradiction. The article also reminds us that the imagery of the Göbekli Cultures may contain cognitive depths and conceptual substrata that remain insufficiently explored, even when a particular interpretation appears overly fixed or reductive.

More broadly, the case reaffirms another principle that has shaped *Neo-Lithics* from its beginning: earlier concepts should be re-tested with new material, as long as this is exposed to scholarly scrutiny. None of us reconstructs the Neolithic from a neutral position. We select, order, emphasise, and narrate. To borrow Ian Hodder's self-ironic formulation, we remain, to a degree, poets of the Neolithic. We construct as much as we reconstruct the worlds we study, and this obliges us to make our assumptions, models, and interpretative risks transparent.

This issue's other contribution, "Neolithic Message at the Bosphorus Summit 2023 in Istanbul" by H.G.K. Gebel, illustrates another part of *Neo-Lithics*' self-understanding. It follows the conviction that archaeologists possess not only a professional competence but also a responsibility to translate the results of their research into reflections useful for present humanity. This may include, and in certain circumstances must include, an intellectual intervention in contemporary conflicts (*cf.* also El Hassan 2025b). The study of Neolithisation cannot be reduced to subsistence, settlement, symbolism, or technology alone. It also concerns the long-term consequences of productive human behaviour: the intensification of human-human conflicts, the expansion of human claims upon nature, and the emergence of new forms of territoriality and commodification, dependency and vulnerability, social and cognitive differentiation.

In this sense, Neolithic research has something to say to the present. It does not provide simple lessons, and it should never become moral propaganda. Yet it can reveal the deep histories of processes that continue to shape us: production and extraction, cooperation and exclusion, resilience and collapse, innovation and violence, care and domination. This is why Prince El Hassan bin Talal's statement at ICHAJ 16 in Athens — "Archaeology is not neutral" — is of particular relevance to us (El Hassan 2025b). Archaeology is not neutral because the past is never merely past. It is mobilised in (enduring) identities, borders, claims, exclusions, reconciliations, and hopes. It can be abused; therefore, it must also be responsibly practised.

The present issue appears at a time when the language of "epochal shifts" has become widespread in Western political discourse. The German term *Zeitenwende* ("turning point") gained particular prominence after the escalation of the war in Ukraine; more recently, "epochal shift" has been invoked in relation to authoritarian populism, renewed nationalism, geopolitical instability, technological acceleration, increasing terrorism, and the return of large-scale military threat and war crimes. Such language reflects real anxieties. Yet it also reveals a specifically Western shock at the destabilisation of assumptions that many societies in Southwest Asia and elsewhere could never take for granted.

For many colleagues working in the Middle East, instability, interrupted projects, postponed fieldwork, threatened archives, damaged institutions, and the personal burden of violence have not been exceptional ruptures but recurring conditions of scholarly life. What is now described in Europe and North America as an epochal transformation has, in many of our working regions, been experienced as a series of continuous or recurring turning points. The Neolithic research family is therefore affected not only logistically and intellectually but also emotionally and ethically, and in parts by direct violence and humanitarian impacts. Research strategies are disrupted, and field projects cannot always proceed as planned. Friendships, institutions, and landscapes of memory are exposed to violence. A general sense of paralysis, insecurity, and diminished optimism has spread or become difficult to ignore.

As prehistorians, however, we have our own understanding of epochal change. In prehistoric periodisation, shifts are not defined by single events or persons. They are identified through long-term transformations in material practice, social organisation, cognitive orientation, environmental relations, and symbolic regimes. The transition from foraging to food-producing lifeways, for example, was not "epochal" in the modern political sense of a rupture. It unfolded through incremental changes over millennia: altered relations to plants and animals, new forms of labour, settlement, property, memory, territoriality, conflict, and cooperation. Its consequences were profound precisely because they reconfigured the foundations of human life.

Modern historical and political periodisations work differently. They mark epochs through dramatic events: the French Revolution of 1789, the fall of the Berlin Wall in 1989, the attacks of 11 September 2001, the Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2022, or the rise of nationalist and anti-democratic movements. Such events matter deeply. Yet their designation as "epochal" is frequently shaped by immediacy, political contingency, and the anxieties of the present. From a prehistoric perspective, we may ask whether they represent foundational transformations or whether they are better understood as symptoms of deeper structural changes that are still unfolding.

This does not mean that archaeology should relativise present suffering and mass killing by situating them within the *longue durée*. On the contrary: the long view increases responsibility. It reminds us that violence, displacement, ecological destruction, and the erosion of trust can have consequences far beyond the moment they occur. It also reminds us that the material and moral structures of societies are inseparable. A true epochal shift is not simply a change of regime, technology, or geopolitical alignment. It occurs when material conditions and moral paradigms are transformed together.

Here, Prince El Hassan's humanistic discourse provides an important counterpoint to purely political narratives of epochal change. In his reflection on Human Solidarity and the Dawn of a New Era (El Hassan 2025b), he calls for a moral and cultural transformation grounded in dignity, justice, compassion, pluralism, diversity, and cooperation. He warns against a world in which the "right of might" overshadows the "might of right", and he insists that charitable sentiment alone cannot address the suffering of the marginalised. What is required is empowerment, institution-building, accountability, and a reorientation of policy towards human dignity.

This is not external to archaeology. Archaeology deals with the conditions under which human communities become capable of living together, producing together, remembering together, and also injuring one another. The Neolithic, in particular, forces us to confront the origins of productive power: the capacity to transform environments, accumulate resources, intensify labour, stabilise settlements, expand symbolic systems, and generate new dependencies. It is therefore one of the deep historical laboratories in which we can study the ambivalence of human achievement. The same processes that enabled cooperation, surplus, and cultural creativity also opened pathways towards inequality, territorial conflict, ecological pressure, and intensified violence.

For this reason, Neolithic research cannot remain enclosed within technical expertise alone. It must continue to refine chronologies, analyse materials, publish evidence, and debate models with methodological discipline. But it must also have the courage to ask what its knowledge means. What does the Neolithic tell us about the price of productivity? What does it reveal about the fragility of coexistence? What does it teach about resilience, adaptation, and the social costs of expansion, acceleration and aggregation? And how can such knowledge contribute, cautiously but meaningfully, to contemporary debates on sustainability, conflict, memory, and human dignity?

The answer is not to instrumentalise archaeology for present agendas. The answer is to practise archaeology with awareness of its consequences. Prince El Hassan's insistence that archaeology is not neutral should be understood in this sense. The archaeologist is not a detached observer of dead worlds. The archaeologist works with evidence that enters living identities, educational systems, heritage politics, territorial narratives, and visions of the future. To excavate, classify, interpret, publish, and narrate is already to participate in the shaping of memory. This participation demands intellectual humility, but it also demands moral clarity.

Is there hope? From a prehistoric perspective, hope cannot be a naïve expectation that history naturally moves towards improvement. The Neolithic itself teaches no simple story of progress. It was a

history of creativity and coercion, cooperation and pressure, prosperity and vulnerability. Yet it also teaches that human societies are capable of profound transformation. They can reorganise their lifeways, reshape their relations with nature, invent new forms of belonging, and create durable frameworks of cooperation. The decisive question is whether such transformation is guided merely by power, fear, and extraction, or by dignity, responsibility, and solidarity.

A conclusion of historical hope must therefore be sober, not sentimental. Our age may indeed become epochal, but not because a single war, leader, ideology, or technology declares it so. It will become epochal only if humanity succeeds in transforming both its material conditions and its moral foundations. The Neolithic research family, working across the landscapes where some of humanity's earliest productive lifeways emerged, has a particular responsibility to keep this deeper perspective alive. We know that human worlds are made; we also know that they can be unmade. Between these two insights lies our obligation.

If archaeology is not neutral, then Neolithic archaeology is not mute. It speaks from the *longue durée* of human becoming, from the first experiments in productive life, and from the landscapes where cooperation and conflict were repeatedly reconfigured. Its message is not despair. Its message is historical responsibility. Hope begins where knowledge refuses indifference.

Hans Georg K. Gebel and Gary Rollefson
(January 2023 and September 2025)

Endnotes

¹ This editorial was written after the individual contributions to *Neo-Lithics 2023* had already been published online, and while the complete issue was being prepared for a compiled publication.

² From 2026, a new editorial team will shape *Neo-Lithics*. It may set different emphases and develop new priorities, while continuing the newsletter's commitment to open, critical, and responsible Neolithic research.

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